

1 A nearly-conservative high-order Lagrange-Galerkin method for the
2 resolution of scalar convection-dominated equations in non-divergence-free
3 velocity fields

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9 **Abstract**

10 In this work, we present a novel Lagrange-Galerkin method for the resolution of the scalar pure-convection
11 and convection-dominated diffusion equations in non-divergence-free velocity fields. The scheme has been
12 formulated so that (i) time-integration is carried out by means of an arbitrary order backward differentiation
13 formula, (ii) finite element space discretizations of any order can be employed, and (iii) it satisfies a discrete
14 mass balance equation at each simulation instant and preserves mass in those cases in which no fluid enters
15 nor leaves the control domain, as long as the integrals involved are computed exactly. These properties are
16 achieved by posing a conservation law for a *weighted mass* –from which the standard mass can be seen as a
17 particular case– that can be easily discretized in time and in space with any order of accuracy. Numerical
18 experiments –which include a three-dimensional test– show that the method is as accurate in time as the
19 employed time-marching formula, as accurate in space as the finite element discretization, and generally more
20 accurate –especially in terms of mass conservation errors– and efficient than the classic, non-conservative
21 Lagrange-Galerkin method. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first conservative Lagrange-Galerkin
22 method for convection-dominated equations that considers both non-divergence-free velocity fields and time
23 and space discretizations of any order.

24 *Keywords:* Lagrange-Galerkin, finite element method, non-divergence-free velocity field,
25 convection-dominated problems, local projection stabilization, high-order methods

26 **1. Introduction**

27 Convection-dominated problems are present nowadays in many fields of science such as aerodynamics [1],
28 combustion [2] and heat transfer [3]. However, its resolution via finite element methods is problematic, since
29 the convective terms of the corresponding equations make the standard Galerkin formulation unstable. As
30 a consequence, several approaches within the finite element methodology have been developed, e.g., Petrov-
31 Galerkin methods [4, 5], pure Lagrangian schemes [6–9], semi-Lagrangian methods [9–14] and Lagrange-
32 Galerkin algorithms [15–18].

33 Among the approaches above, both semi-Lagrange and Lagrange-Galerkin methods are characterized by
34 employing a backward discretization along the flow trajectories of the material derivatives. This results in the
35 following advantages with respect to the other methods [16, 19]: (i) the stabilization of the convective terms
36 is more natural and straightforward, (ii) the formulation leads to linear systems with symmetric matrices

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and (iii) they do not suffer from mesh distortion problems. Additionally, Lagrange-Galerkin schemes are more accurate than semi-Lagrangian methods since they obtain information from previous solutions in terms of L^2 projections and not by interpolations [17].

However, Lagrange-Galerkin methods present a major drawback, which is that they usually fail to preserve mass in those cases in which the latter is constant. To solve this problem, some efforts have been done in the literature. For instance, Benqué et al. [20, 21] presented a conservative method for the case of incompressible flows based on a *weak Lagrange-Galerkin* formulation [22], in which the weighting functions are forced to be constant along the trajectories of the fluid particles. This formulation was applied by Kaazempur-Mofrad et al. [23, 24] to the advection of incompressible flows, and also by Giraldo to the case of the compressible advection equation and linear elements [25] –although he only considers incompressible velocity fields in the numerical examples– and to the case of the shallow water equations [25, 26]. In addition, Rui and Tabata [18] proposed a first-order-in-time conservative method for the convection-diffusion equation in compressible –i.e., non-divergence-free– velocity fields, which consisted on applying the characteristic approximation to a combination of the convective derivative and the divergence term. Mass conservation has also been achieved in pure Lagrangian [6, 8, 27–29] and semi-Lagrangian [11, 12] methods, which are somehow similar to Lagrange-Galerkin algorithms. Nevertheless, to the best of our knowledge, a Lagrange-Galerkin scheme that considers mass conservation, non-divergence-free velocity fields and space and time discretizations of any order is still to be developed.

The latter inconvenience has motivated the consideration in this work of a novel conservative, Lagrange-Galerkin scheme for the resolution of the scalar pure-convection and convection-diffusion equations in the case of non-divergence-free velocity fields. The method is mainly based on formulating a conservation equation for a *weighted mass* –as done in the weak Lagrange-Galerkin formulation [25]– that can be discretized in time and in space with any order of accuracy, and is posed so that the terms that appear in the formulation can be easily computed by means of standard finite element operations. The scheme has been tested on four problems using up to fifth-order finite elements and sixth-order time-marching formulas, and has proved to be generally more accurate than the classic, non-conservative Lagrange-Galerkin formulation in terms of mass conservation and of L^2 errors, as well as more efficient.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows. In Section 2, we introduce a weak conservative formulation for the convection-diffusion equation –the pure convection equation is considered as a particular case– for the continuous model. Then, the resulting equations are discretized as explained in Section 3. Later, in Section 4, some numerical experiments are performed to show the accuracy and efficiency of the new method. Finally, some conclusions are summarized in Section 5.

2. Formulation of the continuous model

In this work, we focus on the convection-diffusion equation for a scalar quantity $u(\mathbf{x}, t)$ within a continuous velocity field $\mathbf{a}(\mathbf{x}, t)$, i.e.,

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\mathbf{a}u) = \nabla \cdot (\epsilon \nabla u), \quad (1)$$

with \mathbf{x} the position vector, t the time and ϵ the so-called diffusion coefficient. For convenience, we consider that \mathbf{a} governs the motion of a fluid, although in reality it may govern the motion of any kind of continuum. We do not assume incompressible flow, i.e., $\nabla \cdot \mathbf{a} \neq 0$ in a general case. Eq. (1) is equivalent to the conservation equation

$$\frac{d}{dt} \int_{\Omega_f} u \, d\Omega = \oint_{\partial\Omega_f} \epsilon \frac{\partial u}{\partial \mathbf{n}} \, d\sigma, \quad (2)$$

with $\Omega_f(t)$ an arbitrary domain that moves with the velocity field –i.e., a fluid volume– and \mathbf{n} the outward normal vector to the surface of Ω_f . In other words, the time derivative of the so-called mass of the fluid volume ($\int_{\Omega_f} u \, d\Omega$) equals the total amount of mass flux $-\epsilon \nabla u$ that enters through the boundary.

79 Let us divide Ω_f into $N \rightarrow \infty$ infinitesimal fluid volumes $\Delta\Omega_k(t)$ of mass $\Delta m_k(t)$. If we apply conservation
80 equation (2) to the k -th infinitesimal fluid volume, then

$$\frac{d}{dt} (\Delta m_k) = \nabla \cdot (\epsilon \nabla u) \Big|_{\mathbf{x}=\mathbf{x}_k} \Delta\Omega_k, \quad (3)$$

81 with $\mathbf{x}_k(t)$ an interior point of the k -th fluid volume, whose trajectory evolves according to $d\mathbf{x}_k(t)/dt =$
82 $\mathbf{a}(\mathbf{x}_k(t), t)$. Now consider a continuous test function $v = v(\mathbf{x}, t)$ that remains constant along the trajectories
83 of the fluid particles, that is, $Dv/Dt := \partial v/\partial t + \mathbf{a} \cdot \nabla v = 0$ or, equivalently, $dv(\mathbf{x}_k(t), t)/dt = 0$ for all k (see Fig.
84 1 for a schematic representation of the variables above). Then, if we multiply equation (3) by $v(\mathbf{x}_k(t), t)$
85 and sum for all the infinitesimal fluid volumes, we arrive at

$$\sum_{k=1}^N \frac{d}{dt} [\Delta m_k(t) v(\mathbf{x}_k(t), t)] = \nabla \cdot (\epsilon \nabla u(\mathbf{x}, t)) \Big|_{\mathbf{x}=\mathbf{x}_k(t)} v(\mathbf{x}_k(t), t) \Delta\Omega_k(t). \quad (4)$$

86 On the other hand, the sum of derivatives is also the derivative of the sum, i.e.,

$$\sum_{k=1}^N \frac{d}{dt} [\Delta m_k(t) v(\mathbf{x}_k(t), t)] = \frac{d}{dt} \left[\sum_{k=1}^N \Delta m_k(t) v(\mathbf{x}_k(t), t) \right]. \quad (5)$$

87 Therefore, if we substitute (5) into (4), make $N \rightarrow \infty$ and operate, we arrive at

$$\frac{d}{dt} \int_{\Omega_f} uv \, d\Omega + \int_{\Omega_f} \epsilon \nabla u \cdot \nabla v \, d\Omega = \oint_{\partial\Omega_f} \epsilon \frac{\partial u}{\partial n} v \, d\sigma. \quad (6)$$

88 Note that (6) can be interpreted from a physical point of view as a conservation balance between the rate of
89 change of a *weighted mass* –first term on the left-hand side–, a weighted measure of the non-uniformity in
90 the density u –second term on the left-hand side– and a *weighted mass flux* over the boundary. That there
91 exists a conservation law for the weighted mass is to be the main key for the conservative schemes developed
92 in this work. Note as well that Eq. (2) can be seen as a particular case of (6) in which $v \equiv 1$.

Figure 1: Scheme with the variables that appear in the derivation of the weak formulation of the continuous model.

93 Also note that, since the test function satisfies $Dv/Dt = 0$, we are implicitly employing the weak
94 Lagrange-Galerkin formulation [20, 21, 23, 25]. However, instead of arriving to (6) by multiplying (1)
95 by v , integrating in Ω_f and using Reynolds theorem [30], which would have been the conventional procedure
96 in this formulation, here we adopt a more “physics-based” approach.

97 3. Numerical discretization

98 3.1. Notation and preliminaries

99 In the following, we assume that Eq. (1) is to be solved at a fixed two-dimensional (control) domain Ω
100 from $t = 0$ to a final time $t = T$. We denote by Ω_h to a polygonal domain that approximates Ω , by \mathbb{T}_h to an
101 admissible decomposition of Ω_h into simplices –although quadrilaterals could be considered as well–, by V_h
102 to a finite element space associated with \mathbb{T}_h and by $u_h^n(\mathbf{x}) \in V_h$ to an approximation to $u(\mathbf{x}, t^n)$, with t^n a

generic time instant. We assume that u_h^n is to be obtained from the solutions $u_h^{n-p}, \dots, u_h^{n-1}$ –also defined in V_h – computed at p previous instants $t^{n-p} < \dots < t^{n-1} < t^n$. In addition, to simplify the integral notation, we denote by

$$(u, v)_D := \int_D uv \, d\Omega, \quad (\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v})_D := \int_D \mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{v} \, d\Omega, \quad \langle u, v \rangle_{\partial D} := \int_{\partial D} uv \, d\sigma, \quad \langle \mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v} \rangle_{\partial D} := \int_{\partial D} \mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{v} \, d\sigma,$$

to the scalar products of two (scalar or vector) functions over a generic domain D and over its boundary ∂D , and by ϕ^{n-l} to any variable $\phi(t)$ evaluated at t^{n-l} .

3.2. The finite element space V_h

With a view to employ subgrid stabilization techniques [16, 31, 32], each function $v_h^n \in V_h$ is to be expressed as the sum

$$v_h^n = \bar{v}_h^n + v_h^{n'} \quad (7)$$

of a *large-scale* term, $\bar{v}_h^n \in \bar{V}_h$, and a *fine-scale* term, $v_h^{n'} \in V_h'$. The spaces \bar{V}_h and V_h' must satisfy some properties such as the existence of a special interpolant and a local inf-sup condition [32]. In this work, \bar{V}_h is as a standard, continuous, polynomial space and V_h' is a bubble space, although there are many other possible choices –also for meshes defined by quadrilaterals– [32].

More specifically, let $\widehat{K} := \{\widehat{\mathbf{x}} \in \mathbb{R}^2 : 0 \leq \widehat{x}_1 \leq 1, 0 \leq \widehat{x}_2 \leq 1 - \widehat{x}_1\}$ be the well-known reference triangle and $r > 0$ the desired order for the space discretization. On \widehat{K} , we define a set of $n_v = (r+1)(r+2)/2$ Chebyshev nodes of the second kind [33], $\widehat{\mathbf{x}}_1, \dots, \widehat{\mathbf{x}}_{n_v}$. If we denote by $\widehat{L}_1, \dots, \widehat{L}_{n_v}$ to the corresponding Lagrange polynomials, then the large scale modes are represented in \widehat{K} by the space

$$\widehat{P}_r(\widehat{K}) := \text{span} \{\widehat{L}_1, \dots, \widehat{L}_{n_v}\},$$

i.e., by means of the polynomials in \widehat{K} with maximal degree r . To obtain explicit expressions for the Lagrange polynomials, we employ the basis defined by the functions

$$\widehat{\psi}_{s,i}(\widehat{\mathbf{x}}) := T_{s-i}(2\widehat{x}_1 - 1)T_i(2\widehat{x}_2 - 1), \quad 0 \leq i \leq s \leq r,$$

with $T_n(\widehat{x})$ the n -th order Chebyshev polynomial of the first kind in the interval $-1 \leq \widehat{x} \leq 1$. For brevity, $\widehat{\psi}_{s,i}$ is to be referred with a single index as $\widehat{\psi}_k$, with $k = (s+1)(s+2)/2 - s + i$, $1 \leq k \leq n_v$ ¹. Then, we write the Lagrange polynomials as

$$\widehat{L}_l(\widehat{\mathbf{x}}) = \sum_{k=1}^{n_v} \widehat{\psi}_k(\widehat{\mathbf{x}}) a_{kl}, \quad l = 1, \dots, n_v,$$

where the coefficients a_{kl} are obtained by imposing $\widehat{L}_l(\widehat{\mathbf{x}}_m) = \delta_{ml}$, with δ_{ml} the Kronecker delta. The latter yields

$$\delta_{ml} = \sum_{k=1}^{n_v} \theta_{mk} a_{kl}, \quad 0 \leq l, m \leq n_v,$$

with $\theta_{mk} := \widehat{\psi}_k(\widehat{\mathbf{x}}_m)$ a generalized Vandermonde matrix. Therefore, $a_{kl} = [\theta^{-1}]_{kl}$ and

$$\widehat{L}_l(\widehat{\mathbf{x}}) = \sum_{k=1}^{n_v} \widehat{\psi}_k(\widehat{\mathbf{x}}) [\theta^{-1}]_{kl}, \quad l = 1, \dots, n_v.$$

It must be remarked that the basis $\{\widehat{\psi}_1, \dots, \widehat{\psi}_{n_v}\}$ is not orthogonal in \widehat{K} , and therefore it can lead to ill-conditioning problems in the Vandermonde matrix θ for the case of very high order discretizations. This drawback could be alleviated by considering the orthogonal Prorior-Koornwinder-Dubiner basis [34–37] instead –see, e.g. [38]. However, the basis employed above is simpler to implement and performs well enough for the cases considered in this work ($r \leq 5$).

¹Note that k denotes the position of $\widehat{\psi}_{s,i}$ in the list $\{\widehat{\psi}_{0,0}, \widehat{\psi}_{1,0}, \widehat{\psi}_{0,1}, \dots, \widehat{\psi}_{r,0}, \dots, \widehat{\psi}_{r,r}\}$.

132 Furthermore, we define the bubble function as

$$\widehat{b} := 27(1 - \widehat{x}_1 - \widehat{x}_2)\widehat{x}_1\widehat{x}_2$$

133 Note that \widehat{b} is a third-order polynomial and that it equals 0 at the edges/faces of the element and 1 at its
134 barycenter. Then, the fine scale modes are represented in \widehat{K} by the enrichment space

$$\widehat{B}_{r-1}(\widehat{K}) := \begin{cases} \text{span}\{\widehat{b}\}, & r = 1, \\ \text{span}\{\widehat{b}\widehat{\psi}_{r-2,0}, \dots, \widehat{b}\widehat{\psi}_{r-2,r-2}, \widehat{b}\widehat{\psi}_{r-1,0}, \dots, \widehat{b}\widehat{\psi}_{r-1,r-1}\}, & r > 1. \end{cases}$$

135 That is, for $r > 1$, \widehat{B}_{r-1} is the space spanned by the products of the bubble function and the polynomials
136 of degree at least $r - 2$ and at most $r - 1$. Note that the products of \widehat{b} and the polynomials of degree lower
137 than $r - 2$ are disregarded as basis functions for \widehat{B}_{r-1} as they are polynomials of degree at most r , and thus
138 they are actually contained in the large-scale space \widehat{P}_r . See example in Fig. 2.

Figure 2: Basis functions of the space \widehat{B}_1 normalized with their maximum absolute value.

139 Hence, our finite element space reads in \widehat{K} as

$$\widehat{V} = \widehat{P}_r^{\text{bubble}}(\widehat{K}) := \widehat{P}_r(\widehat{K}) \oplus \widehat{B}_{r-1}(\widehat{K}).$$

140 Of course, the latter spaces can be expressed in terms of the mesh elements –instead of the reference
141 element– by considering the well-known isoparametric transformation

$$\mathbf{F}_K : \widehat{\mathbf{x}} \in \widehat{K} \longrightarrow \mathbf{x} \in K, \quad \mathbf{x} = \sum_{i=1}^{n_v} \mathbf{x}_{n_i} \widehat{L}_i(\widehat{\mathbf{x}}), \quad (8)$$

142 between \widehat{K} and a given element $K \in \mathbb{T}_h$, with \mathbf{x}_{n_i} the coordinates of the i -th local node of K . In that case,
143 the large scale and the fine scale terms are represented, respectively, by the spaces

$$\begin{aligned} P_r(\mathbb{T}_h) &:= \{v \in C^0(\Omega_h) : v|_K = \widehat{v} \circ \mathbf{F}_K^{-1}, \widehat{v} \in \widehat{P}_r(\widehat{K}), \forall K \in \mathbb{T}_h\}, \\ B_{r-1}(\mathbb{T}_h) &:= \{v \in C^0(\Omega_h) : v|_K = \widehat{v} \circ \mathbf{F}_K^{-1}, \widehat{v} \in \widehat{B}_{r-1}(\widehat{K}), \forall K \in \mathbb{T}_h\}, \end{aligned}$$

144 that is, $\overline{v}_h^n \in P_r(\mathbb{T}_h)$ and $v_h^{n'} \in B_{r-1}(\mathbb{T}_h)$ in Eq. (7). Furthermore,

$$V_h := \{v \in C^0(\Omega_h) : v|_K = \widehat{v} \circ \mathbf{F}_K^{-1}, \widehat{v} \in \widehat{V}(\widehat{K}), \forall K \in \mathbb{T}_h\}.$$

145 Note that $V_h = P_r^{\text{bubble}}(\mathbb{T}_h) := P_r(\mathbb{T}_h) \oplus B_{r-1}(\mathbb{T}_h)$. The reader is referred to [32] for more details.

146 3.3. Convection of fluid particles, elements and test functions

147 Eq. (6) forces us to consider an integration domain $\Omega_f(t)$ that moves with the fluid flow, as well as
148 test functions $v(\mathbf{x}, t)$ that remain constant along the fluid trajectories. Therefore, before discretizing this
149 equation in time, it is convenient to explain how the fluid domain $\Omega_f(t)$ is to be approximated at a generic

instant $t^{n-l} < t^n$, assuming that $\Omega_f(t)$ is chosen so that it coincides with Ω_h at t^n –i.e., $\Omega_f^n \equiv \Omega_h$. Likewise, it must be specified how $v(\mathbf{x}, t^{n-l})$ is to be approximated, assuming that $v(\mathbf{x}, t^n) = v_h^n \in V_h$.

For that purpose, we focus first on the computation of the trajectories of the fluid particles in Ω_h from t^n backwards to t^{n-l} . We denote by $\mathbf{X}(\mathbf{x}, t^n; t)$ to the position at time t of a fluid particle that occupies the position \mathbf{x} at t^n and by $\mathbf{X}^{n-l}(\mathbf{x}) := \mathbf{X}(\mathbf{x}, t^n; t^{n-l})$ for short. First, we convect the N_h mesh nodes $\{\mathbf{x}_i\}_{i=1}^{N_h}$ from t^n to t^{n-l} by solving the differential equation

$$\begin{cases} \frac{d\mathbf{X}(\mathbf{x}_i, t^n; t)}{dt} = \mathbf{a}(\mathbf{X}(\mathbf{x}_i, t^n; t), t), & t^{n-l} \leq t \leq t^n, \\ \mathbf{X}(\mathbf{x}_i, t^n; t^n) = \mathbf{x}_i, \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

for $i = 1, \dots, N_h$ with a p -th order, explicit Runge-Kutta. The Runge-Kutta methods employed in this work are specified in Table 1. Now, for each element $K \in \mathbb{T}_h$, we define an isoparametric *convected element* \tilde{K}_h^{n-l} from the convected nodes of K . That is, \tilde{K}_h^{n-l} is the image of the isoparametric transformation

$$\tilde{\mathbf{F}}_K^{n-l} : \tilde{\mathbf{x}} \in \tilde{K} \longrightarrow \mathbf{X} \in \tilde{K}_h^{n-l}, \quad \mathbf{X} = \sum_{i=1}^{n_v} \mathbf{X}^{n-l}(\mathbf{x}_{n_i}) \tilde{L}_i(\tilde{\mathbf{x}}),$$

with \mathbf{x}_{n_i} the coordinates of the i -th local node of K . Note that \tilde{K}_h^{n-l} is an approximation to the *exactly convected element* $\tilde{K}^{n-l} := \{\mathbf{X} : \mathbf{X} = \mathbf{X}^{n-l}(\mathbf{x}), \mathbf{x} \in K\}$. Then, for each \mathbf{x} in a given $K \in \mathbb{T}_h$ that is not a node of the mesh, instead of computing $\mathbf{X}^{n-l}(\mathbf{x})$ exactly by solving (9), we obtain an approximation $\mathbf{X}_h^{n-l}(\mathbf{x})$ which satisfies: (i) $\mathbf{X}_h^{n-l}(\mathbf{x}) \in \tilde{K}_h^{n-l}$, and (ii) $\mathbf{X}_h^{n-l}(\mathbf{x})$ and \mathbf{x} share the same natural coordinates in the reference element [17, 39]. That is,

$$\mathbf{X}^{n-l}(\mathbf{x}) \simeq \mathbf{X}_h^{n-l}(\mathbf{x}) := \tilde{\mathbf{F}}_K^{n-l}(\mathbf{F}_K^{-1}(\mathbf{x})). \quad (10)$$

Note that the error of the latter approximation is consistent with the space discretization, i.e., $|\mathbf{X}^{n-l}(\mathbf{x}) - \mathbf{X}_h^{n-l}(\mathbf{x})| \sim \mathcal{O}(h^{r+1})$. Also note that we assume that the triangle \tilde{K}_h^{n-l} is not distorted, which in practice is satisfied unless the time step $t^n - t^{n-l}$ is too large. In effect, recall that mesh distortion appears typically in “forward” Lagrangian methods [7, 8] after the initial mesh is displaced during a noticeable lapse of time. Therefore, mesh distortion should not be expected if the mesh is displaced only during a reasonable time step with a smooth velocity field. In any case, it can be checked that \tilde{K}_h^{n-l} is not distorted by proceeding as shown in [40].

Table 1: List of the Runge-Kutta methods employed in this work.

p	Method
1	Forward Euler
2	Explicit midpoint
3	Strong stability preserving Runge-Kutta [41]
4	Ralston [42]
5	Runge-Kutta-Fehlberg [43]
6	Luther [44]

For convenience, we also define the *convected mesh* $\tilde{\mathbb{T}}_h^{n-l}$ as that composed by the convected elements, i.e.,

$$\tilde{\mathbb{T}}_h^{n-l} := \bigcup_{K \in \mathbb{T}_h} \tilde{K}_h^{n-l},$$

and the *convected volume* $\tilde{\Omega}_h^{n-l}$ as the geometric place that results from convecting the fluid particles in Ω_h from t^n to t^{n-l} with approximation (10), i.e.,

$$\tilde{\Omega}_h^{n-l} := \{\mathbf{X} \in \mathbb{R}^d : \mathbf{X} = \mathbf{X}_h^{n-l}(\mathbf{x}), \mathbf{x} \in \Omega_h\}.$$

175 It is clear now that, if $\Omega_f^n \equiv \Omega_h$, then Ω_f^{n-l} can be approximated by $\tilde{\Omega}_h^{n-l}$. In addition, $\tilde{\mathbb{T}}_h^{n-l}$ is a decomposition
 176 of $\tilde{\Omega}_h^{n-l}$ into isoparametric (curvilinear) elements.

177 Finally, let us consider a function $v_h(\mathbf{x}, t)$ which satisfies $Dv_h/Dt = 0$ and $v_h^n(\mathbf{x}) \in V_h$. Since v_h is constant
 178 along the fluid trajectories, we can make the approximation $v_h^{n-l}(\mathbf{X}_h^{n-l}(\mathbf{x})) = v_h^n(\mathbf{x})$. Moreover, v_h^{n-l} belongs
 179 to the *convected finite element space*

$$\tilde{V}_h^{n-l} := \{v_h^{n-l} : v_h^{n-l}(\mathbf{X}_h^{n-l}(\mathbf{x})) = v_h^n(\mathbf{x}) \in V_h\}.$$

180 Recall that $\mathbf{X}_h^{n-l}(\mathbf{x})$ and \mathbf{x} share the same natural coordinates in \hat{K} . As a consequence, v_h^{n-l} and v_h^n read
 181 the same when expressed in terms of natural coordinates in the reference element, that is,

$$v_h^{n-l}|_{\tilde{K}_h^{n-l}} \circ \tilde{\mathbf{F}}_K^{n-l} = v_h^n|_K \circ \mathbf{F}_K = \hat{v}_h \in \hat{V}(\hat{K}), \quad \forall K \in \mathbb{T}_h,$$

182 and hence \tilde{V}_h^{n-l} is also a P_r^{bubble} space, but associated with the mesh $\tilde{\mathbb{T}}_h^{n-l}$ instead of \mathbb{T}_h , i.e., $\tilde{V}_h^{n-l} =$
 183 $P_r^{\text{bubble}}(\tilde{\mathbb{T}}_h^{n-l})$. The latter point is the main key for discretizing Eq. (6) in time and in space.

184 See also Fig. 3 for an explanatory scheme of the computation of the trajectories of the fluid particles.

Figure 3: Scheme to illustrate the computation of the fluid trajectories for the case of quadratic triangular elements. First, we convect the mesh nodes (gray trajectories) according to system (9). From the convected nodes, we construct new isoparametric elements (green) and convect the inner points of the elements so that each $\mathbf{x} \in K$ and $\mathbf{X}_h^{n-l}(\mathbf{x}) \in \tilde{K}_h^{n-l}$ (red trajectory) share the same natural coordinates $\hat{\mathbf{x}}$ in the reference element \hat{K} .

185 3.4. Discretization of the pure convection equation

186 For simplicity, we approach first the case in which there is no diffusion. When $\epsilon = 0$, Eq. (6) simplifies
 187 to

$$(u^n, v^n)_{\Omega_f^n} = (u^{n-1}, v^{n-1})_{\Omega_f^{n-1}}$$

188 which, according to Section 3.3, can be discretized as

$$(u_h^n, v_h^n)_{\Omega_h} = (u_h^{n-1}, v_h^{n-1})_{\tilde{\Omega}_h^{n-1}}, \quad \forall v_h^n \in V_h. \quad (11)$$

189 We strongly remark that, if v_h^n is the i -th shape function of V_h , then v_h^{n-1} is the i -th shape function of \tilde{V}_h^{n-1}
 190 –assuming the degrees of freedom are numbered in the same way in both spaces. In addition, \tilde{V}_h^{n-1} is a

191 conventional P_r^{bubble} space associated with $\tilde{\mathbb{T}}_h^{n-1}$. The initial value u_h^0 is taken as the L^2 projection of the
 192 initial condition $u^0(\mathbf{x})$, i.e.,

$$(u_h^0, v_h^0)_{\Omega_h} = (u^0(\mathbf{x}), v_h^0)_{\Omega_h}, \quad \forall v_h^0 \in V_h. \quad (12)$$

193 It must be pointed that the right-hand side in (11) involves the product of u_h^{n-1} , which is defined
 194 piecewise in \mathbb{T}_h , and v_h^{n-1} , which is defined piecewise in $\tilde{\mathbb{T}}_h^{n-1}$ (see Fig. 4). Since these two meshes are
 195 generally different, one needs mesh intersection techniques to accurately compute this term [45–47], or to
 196 integrate with respect to the elements in $\tilde{\mathbb{T}}_h^{n-1}$ with high-order quadrature rules [48]. Although we recognize
 197 that mesh intersection techniques may lead to better accuracy, in the present work we have adopted the
 198 second approach for simplicity.

199 If the right-hand side of (11) is computed with high-order quadrature rules [48], we can proceed as if
 200 $u_h^{n-1}(\mathbf{x})$ were a given function and we had to compute the scalar product of $u_h^{n-1}(\mathbf{x})$ and the basis functions
 201 of \tilde{V}_h^{n-1} . Since the latter is a standard P_r^{bubble} space associated with $\tilde{\mathbb{T}}_h^{n-1}$, this would be a very conventional
 202 operation within the finite element methodology. More specifically,

$$(u_h^{n-1}, v_h^{n-1})_{\tilde{\Omega}_h^{n-1}} \simeq \sum_{\tilde{K}_h^{n-1} \in \tilde{\mathbb{T}}_h^{n-1}} \sum_{k=1}^{n_q} w_k u_h^{n-1}(\tilde{\mathbf{F}}_K^{n-1}(\tilde{\boldsymbol{\xi}}_k)) \hat{v}_h(\tilde{\boldsymbol{\xi}}_k) \det \left(\frac{\partial \tilde{\mathbf{F}}_K^{n-1}(\tilde{\mathbf{x}})}{\partial \tilde{\mathbf{x}}} \right)_{\tilde{\mathbf{x}}=\tilde{\boldsymbol{\xi}}_k},$$

203 with n_q the number of quadrature points, $\tilde{\boldsymbol{\xi}}_1, \dots, \tilde{\boldsymbol{\xi}}_{n_q}$ the quadrature nodes in \tilde{K} and w_1, \dots, w_{n_q} the weights
 204 of the quadrature formula. The only aspect that must be noted is that u_h^{n-1} is not explicitly known in terms
 205 of \mathbf{x} , but in terms of natural coordinates along the elements in \mathbb{T}_h , and thus we need a search-locate algorithm
 206 [49, 50] to evaluate u_h^{n-1} at the quadrature points of $\tilde{\mathbb{T}}_h^{n-1}$.

207 Also observe that, when there is flow entering the domain through part of the boundary –i.e., $\mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{n} < 0$ –,
 208 part of the convected domain $\tilde{\Omega}_h^{n-1}$ –in which the integral in the right-hand side of (11) is defined– lies
 209 outside of the domain Ω_h –in which the previous solution u_h^{n-1} is defined (see also Fig. 4). In those cases,
 210 we assume that u_h^{n-1} is equal to some known (incoming) flow conditions in the region $\tilde{\Omega}_h^{n-1} \setminus \Omega_h$ in order
 211 to compute the right-hand side of (11). Note that this procedure is a way of weakly imposing Dirichlet
 212 conditions at the boundary through which the fluid enters.

Figure 4: Scheme that illustrates the domains and meshes that appear in the formulation. The elements in \mathbb{T}_h are convected backwards in time with the flow velocity field to form $\tilde{\mathbb{T}}_h^{n-1}$. The variables u_h^n , v_h^n and u_h^{n-1} are defined piecewise in \mathbb{T}_h , whereas v_h^{n-1} is defined piecewise in $\tilde{\mathbb{T}}_h^{n-1}$.

213 Although (11) may be a valid scheme, it is convenient to add a stabilization term to avoid instabilities
 214 derived from the inaccuracies in the computation of the right-hand side term [16]. In our case, we have
 215 adopted the local projection stabilization (LPS) method [16, 31, 32], which consists in adding some kind of

diffusion in the fine-scale terms of the solution. Although there are many possible ways of performing the LPS –see, e.g., [32]–, here we have proceeded as follows. Let

$$Q_{r-1} := \{v : v|_K = \widehat{v} \circ \mathbf{F}_K^{-1}, \widehat{v} \in \widehat{P}_{r-1}(\widehat{K}), \forall K \in \mathbb{T}_h\}$$

be a discontinuous space associated with \mathbb{T}_h , π_h the projection operator onto Q_{r-1} , \mathbb{I} the identity operator, and $\kappa_h := \mathbb{I} - \pi_h$ the fluctuation operator with respect to Q_{r-1} . Then, we add a diffusion term of the form

$$S_{\text{LPS}}(u_h^n, v_h^n) := \sum_{K \in \mathbb{T}_h} C_{\text{LPS}} a_K h_K \int_K \kappa_h \nabla u_h^n \cdot \kappa_h \nabla v_h^n \, d\Omega$$

to the left-hand side of Eq. (11), yielding

$$(u_h^n, v_h^n)_{\Omega_h} + \Delta t^n S_{\text{LPS}}(u_h^n, v_h^n) = (u_h^{n-1}, v_h^{n-1})_{\widehat{\Omega}_h^{n-1}}, \quad \forall v_h^n \in V_h, \quad (13)$$

which is the final scheme used in this work. Here, C_{LPS} is a (dimensionless) user-defined constant, a_K is a characteristic speed, h_K is a length related to the size of the element K , and $\Delta t^n := t^n - t^{n-1}$ denotes the current time step size. Note that $C_{\text{LPS}} a_K h_K$ has dimensions of length square into time, that is, the same as a diffusion constant. Following [16, 31], we have set $C_{\text{LPS}} = 10^2$, $a_K = 1$ –as usual, physical units are omitted– and $h_K = [\int_K d\Omega]^{1/d}$. Recalling decomposition (7) and that $\bar{v}_h^n \in P_r$, it can be seen that $\kappa_h \nabla \bar{v}_h^n = \mathbf{0}$ for all $v_h^n \in V_h$. Thus, the term S_{LPS} represents some kind of diffusion that is applied only to the fine-scale terms.

Despite it might be seen as a minor detail, it is convenient to point out that in this work Δt^n is forced to equal a fixed, given time step Δt , excepting the (one or two) last steps of the simulation, in which the time step is clipped so that the last simulated t^n coincides exactly with a given final time T . More specifically, given t^n , a target time step Δt , and a minimum time step size Δt^{\min} , t^{n+1} is computed as

$$t^{n+1} = \text{tn_update}(t^n, T, \Delta t, \Delta t^{\min}) := \begin{cases} t^n + \Delta t & \text{if } t^n + \Delta t < T - \Delta t^{\min}, \\ T - \Delta t^{\min} & \text{if } T - \Delta t^{\min} \leq t^n + \Delta t < T, \\ T & \text{if } t^n + \Delta t \geq T. \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

Note that we do not simply take $t^{n+1} = \min\{t^n + \Delta t, T\}$ in order to prevent the scheme from eventually taking too small time steps that may cause underflow errors. In the numerical examples, we have set $\Delta t^{\min} = 10^{-6}$.

Summarizing, the scheme for the pure-convection equation reads as in Algorithm 1.

Algorithm 1: LPS, conservative, Lagrange-Galerkin method for the pure convection equation.

Data: $u^0(\mathbf{x})$, Ω_h , \mathbb{T}_h , V_h , T , Δt , Δt^{\min} , p .

1 **set** $n = 0$, $t^0 = 0$,

2 **compute** u_h^0 by solving (12),

3 **while** $t^n < T$ **do**

4 **update** $n \leftarrow n + 1$,

5 **set** $t^n = \text{tn_update}(t^{n-1}, T, \Delta t, \Delta t^{\min})$,

6 **convect** nodes of \mathbb{T}_h from t^n to t^{n-1} by solving (9) with a p -th order explicit Runge-Kutta method,

7 **compute** u_h^n by solving (13),

8 **end**

Result: $u_h(\mathbf{x}, T)$.

Finally, let us point some properties about scheme (13):

(i) Since $v_h^n \equiv 1$ belongs to the test space V_h , scheme (13) satisfies

$$\int_{\Omega_h} u_h^n \, d\Omega = \int_{\widehat{\Omega}_h^{n-1}} u_h^{n-1} \, d\Omega, \quad (15)$$

that is, it preserves mass in the fluid volume as long as the integrals in the formulation are computed exactly. Note that the latter is achieved if the right-hand side term in (13) is computed with mesh

240 intersection techniques. However, if this term is computed via high-order quadrature rules, as is our
 241 case, Eq. (15) is not satisfied exactly, but only with high accuracy. Therefore, we shall say that the
 242 method proposed in this work is *nearly* conservative.

243 (ii) As a consequence of Eq. (15), if the fluid domain and the control domain are coincident –i.e., $\mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{n} = 0$
 244 in $\partial\Omega_h^-$, then scheme (13) (nearly) preserves mass in the control volume.

245 (iii) When Δt^n remains fixed, Eq. (13) leads to a linear system whose matrix is constant and symmetric
 246 positive definite. Since this system has to be solved many times, the Cholesky decomposition of the
 247 matrix can be reused [51] to achieve a better efficiency.

248 3.5. Discretization of the convection-diffusion equation

249 When $\epsilon \neq 0$, Eq. (6) can be discretized by means of an adaptive k -step backward differentiation formula
 250 (BDF k) as

$$\sum_{l=0}^k \alpha_l (u_h^{n-l}, v_h^{n-l})_{\tilde{\Omega}_h^{n-l}} + \Delta t^n (\epsilon \nabla u_h^n, \nabla v_h^n)_{\Omega_h} + \Delta t^n S_{\text{LPS}}(u_h^n, v_h^n) = \Delta t^n \left\langle \epsilon \frac{\partial u^n}{\partial n}, v_h^n \right\rangle_{\partial\Omega_h}, \quad \forall v_h^n \in V_h. \quad (16)$$

251 Here, $\Delta t^n := t^n - t^{n-1}$ denotes again the current time step and the α_l 's are the weights of the BDF k , which
 252 can be computed from the derivatives at $t = t^n$ of the Lagrange polynomials associated with the nodes
 253 t^{n-k}, \dots, t^n , i.e.,

$$\alpha_l = \sum_{\substack{i=0 \\ i \neq l}}^k \frac{\Delta t^n}{t^{n-l} - t^{n-i}} \prod_{\substack{j=0 \\ j \neq i, l}}^k \frac{t^n - t^{n-j}}{t^{n-l} - t^{n-j}}. \quad (17)$$

254 Note that the LPS has been included, that u^n is not approximated by u_h^n at the boundary and that the
 255 terms in Eq. (16) can be computed in a way similar to those of Eq. (13), excepting the boundary integral.

256 The boundary term in (16) is treated as usual in the literature. We assume that $\partial\Omega_h$ is divided in two
 257 regions, Γ_N and Γ_D , in which Neumann and Dirichlet boundary conditions are applied, i.e.,

$$\begin{aligned} u(\mathbf{x}, t) &= u_D(\mathbf{x}, t), & \mathbf{x} \in \Gamma_D, \\ q(\mathbf{x}, t) &:= -\epsilon \frac{\partial u(\mathbf{x}, t)}{\partial n} = q_N(\mathbf{x}, t), & \mathbf{x} \in \Gamma_N, \end{aligned}$$

258 with $u_D(\mathbf{x}, t)$ and $q_N(\mathbf{x}, t)$ given functions. For convenience, we define the auxiliary spaces

$$\begin{aligned} V_{hD} &:= \{v_h^n \in V_h : v_h|_{\Gamma_D} = L_h u_D(\mathbf{x}, t^n)\}, \\ V_{h0} &:= \{v_h^n \in V_h : v_h|_{\Gamma_D} = 0\}, \end{aligned}$$

259 with L_h the Lagrange interpolation operator onto \mathbb{T}_h . Then, we find $u_h^n \in V_{hD}$ such that

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_0 (u_h^n, v_h^n)_{\Omega_h} + \Delta t^n (\epsilon \nabla u_h^n, \nabla v_h^n)_{\Omega_h} + \Delta t^n S_{\text{LPS}}(u_h^n, v_h^n) = \\ - \Delta t^n \langle q_N^n, v_h^n \rangle_{\Gamma_N} - \sum_{l=1}^k \alpha_l (u_h^{n-l}, v_h^{n-l})_{\tilde{\Omega}_h^{n-l}}, \quad \forall v_h^n \in V_{h0}. \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

260 After that, the unknown mass flux across Γ_D can be computed by making $v_h^n \equiv 1$ in (16), which yields

$$Q_D^n := \int_{\Gamma_D} q^n d\sigma = - \sum_{l=1}^k \frac{\alpha_l}{\Delta t^n} \int_{\tilde{\Omega}_h^{n-l}} u_h^{n-l} d\Omega - \int_{\Gamma_N} q_N^n d\sigma \quad (19)$$

261 The method is started with a BDF n for the initial steps $n = 1, \dots, p-1$ and then is always advanced with
 262 a BDF p –i.e., $k = \min\{n, p\}$ in (16)-(18). In addition, if $p > 1$, the time step is progressively increased from a
 263 small initial value to a target value in order for the errors in those initial steps not to become dominant and

264 spoil the p -th order time convergence rate of the method. More specifically, given a time step parameter
 265 Δt , we set an initial target time step $\tau^0 = \Delta t/2^{10}$, which is updated along the simulation according to the
 266 formula $\tau^{n+1} = \min\{\rho\tau^n, \Delta t\}$, with $\rho > 1$ a constant factor to be discussed later. Meanwhile, t^n is updated
 267 with the formula $t^{n+1} = \text{tn_update}(t^n, T, \tau^n, \Delta t^{\min})$. Recall that, according to (14), the real time step Δt^n
 268 equals the target time step τ^n , excepting the (one or two) last steps of the simulation. Hence, the method
 269 is started with a very small time step, which is progressively increased until it reaches a maximum value
 270 Δt . Then, the time step remains fixed until the last steps of the simulation, in which it is clipped so that
 271 the last simulated instant t^n equals T .

272 As it is known from the theory of BDF, the stability of formula (18) is governed by the eigenvalues of
 273 the stiffness and of the LPS matrices with changed sign. Since the latter are positive semidefinite, these
 274 eigenvalues are real and negative. Therefore, if we want that the method be stable for any Δt^n , formula (18)
 275 must be $A0$ -stable, i.e., its stability region must contain the real negative semiaxis. Note that this is less
 276 restrictive than the usual A-stability condition. A0-stability is automatically satisfied for all known BDF
 277 when the time step is fixed. However, in the adaptive case, ρ must respect an upper bound, which can be
 278 computed –for each p – as shown in [52]. In this work, we have employed the values of ρ detailed in Table 2.

Table 2: Values of ρ for each time order p .

p	2	3	4	5	6
ρ	2.41	1.58	1.25	1.10	1.02

279 The scheme for the convection-diffusion equation is summarized in Algorithm 2.

Algorithm 2: LPS, conservative, Lagrange-Galerkin method for the convection-diffusion equation.

Data: $u^0(\mathbf{x})$, Ω_h , \mathbb{T}_h , V_h , T , Δt , Δt^{\min} , p , ρ .
 1 **set** $n = 0$, $t^0 = 0$, $\tau^0 = \Delta t/2^{10}$,
 2 **compute** u_h^0 by solving (12),
 3 **while** $t^n < T$ **do**
 4 **update** $n \leftarrow n + 1$,
 5 **set** $t^n = \text{tn_update}(t^{n-1}, T, \tau^{n-1}, \Delta t^{\min})$, $\tau^n = \min\{\rho\tau^{n-1}, \Delta t\}$,
 6 **set** $k = \min\{n, p\}$,
 7 **convect** nodes of \mathbb{T}_h from t^n to t^{n-1}, \dots, t^{n-k} by solving (9) with a p -th order explicit Runge-Kutta
 method,
 8 **compute** coefficients α_l of the BDF k from Eq. (17),
 9 **compute** u_h^n by solving (18),
 10 **end**
Result: $u_h(\mathbf{x}, T)$.

281 Finally, let us make a few remarks about scheme (18):

282 (i) If the mass flux across Γ_D is computed according to (19), obviously, the proposed scheme satisfies the
 283 discrete mass balance

$$\sum_{l=0}^k \alpha_l \int_{\bar{\Omega}_h^{n-l}} u_h^{n-l} d\Omega + \Delta t^n \left[\int_{\Gamma_N} q_N^n d\sigma + Q_D^n \right] = 0 \quad (20)$$

284 for the fluid domain, as long as the integrals in the formulation are computed exactly. Recall that the
 285 latter requires that mesh intersection techniques be employed; if high-order quadrature rules are used,
 286 as is our case, (20) is satisfied only with high accuracy.

287 (ii) As a consequence of (20), if the fluid domain and the control domain are coincident $-\mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{n} = 0$ in
 288 $\partial\Omega_{h-}$ and there is no mass flux through the boundary $-q_N^n = 0$ and $\Gamma_N \equiv \partial\Omega_{h-}$, scheme (18) (nearly)
 289 preserves mass in the control domain.

290 (iii) As it happened in the case of the pure convection equation, Eq. (18) leads to a linear system whose
 291 matrix is constant –whenever Δt^n and the α_l 's remain fixed– and symmetric positive definite. Since

292 this system has to be solved many times, the Cholesky decomposition of the matrix can be reused [51]
 293 to achieve a better efficiency.

294 4. Numerical experiments

295 In this section, we first test conservative schemes (13) and (18) on four different problems and compare
 296 the results to those obtained with the conventional, non-conservative Lagrange-Galerkin method reviewed
 297 in Appendix A. In particular, we focus on the convergence rate of the normalized L^2 and mass errors at the
 298 final time T , defined respectively as

$$e_{L^2} := \left[\frac{\int_{\Omega_h} [u_h(\mathbf{x}, T) - u(\mathbf{x}, T)]^2 d\Omega(\mathbf{x})}{\int_{\Omega_h} u^2(\mathbf{x}, t) d\Omega(\mathbf{x})} \right]^{1/2}, \quad e_m := \frac{|\int_{\Omega_h} [u_h(\mathbf{x}, T) - u(\mathbf{x}, T)] d\Omega(\mathbf{x})|}{\int_{\Omega_h} u(\mathbf{x}, t) d\Omega(\mathbf{x})},$$

299 with respect to the mesh size h and the time step parameter Δt . We shall see if the L^2 error in schemes
 300 (13) and (18) converge as expected in semi-Lagrangian and Lagrange-Galerkin methods, i.e. [53–55],

$$e_{L^2} = \mathcal{O}(\Delta t^p) + \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{h^{r+1}}{\Delta t}\right) \quad (21)$$

301 as long as $a_0 \Delta t / h \gtrsim 1$, with $a_0 = \max |\mathbf{a}(\mathbf{x}, t)|$ the characteristic velocity. Afterwards, we perform some
 302 additional simulations to compare the computational efficiency of the conservative method with that of the
 303 non-conservative one, [and show some work-precision diagrams of the conservative method.](#)

304 In Tests I-III, the domain is the square $[-1, 1]^2$, the meshes are generated with GMSH software [56] and
 305 the mesh size is defined as $h = \sqrt{(4|\Omega_h|/\sqrt{3}N_E)}$, with $|\Omega_h| = \int_{\Omega_h} d\Omega$ and N_E the number of elements –i.e., if
 306 all the elements were equilateral triangles of the same size, h would represent the side sizes of those triangles.
 307 We consider $r \leq 5$ for the space discretization and $p \leq 6$ for the time discretization. The integrals in the
 308 formulation are evaluated via 175-node quadrature rules [57], which are exact for 30th-degree polynomials.
 309 The codes for these tests were implemented in Julia language [58].

310 On the other hand, Test IV is an extension of Test II to the three-dimensional case. For this test, we
 311 adapted an old code [17] written in C language that employs the tetrahedral mesh generator MMG3D [59]
 312 and defined the mesh size as $h = \sqrt[3]{6\sqrt{2}|\Omega_h|/N_E}$ –i.e., if all the elements were regular tetrahedra of the
 313 same size, h would represent the side sizes of those tetrahedra. The domain is the cube $[-1, 1]^3$. It must
 314 be pointed that this three-dimensional code only considers $r \leq 2$ and 24-node quadrature rules [60] –which
 315 are exact for 6th-degree polynomials–, and does not employ the LPS –i.e., it considers the standard P_1
 316 and P_2 elements. However, the results are still valuable to illustrate the applicability of our method to the
 317 three-dimensional case.

318 4.1. Test I

319 Test I consists on a pure convection problem –i.e., $\epsilon = 0$ – given by the data

$$\mathbf{a}(\mathbf{x}, t) = [0.5 \sin(\pi x_1) \cos(0.5\pi t), -0.25 \sin(\pi x_2) \cos(0.5\pi t)]^T, \quad u(\mathbf{x}, 0) = \exp\left(-\frac{x_1^2 + x_2^2}{0.045}\right), \quad T = 1.$$

320 Note that $\mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{n} = 0$ at the boundary, and thus mass must be preserved along time. In addition, the trajectories
 321 of the fluid particles can be analytically computed for this problem, which allows to obtain the analytical
 322 solution through the formula $u(\mathbf{x}, T) = u^0(\mathbf{X}(\mathbf{x}, T; 0)) \det(\partial \mathbf{X}(\mathbf{x}, T; 0) / \partial \mathbf{x})$ [11]. The evolution of the
 323 solution from $t = 0$ to $t = T$ is represented in Fig. 5.

Figure 5: Numerical solution of Test I at different time instants. The horizontal and vertical axis correspond to the x_1 and x_2 coordinates, respectively.

324 Fig. 6 shows the variation of the errors with respect to the parameter Δt for a fixed space discretization.
 325 As can be seen, for large Δt 's, the L^2 error behaves as $\mathcal{O}(\Delta t^p)$, both for the conservative and non-conservative
 326 methods, as expected, although the errors are lower for the conservative scheme than for the non-conservative
 327 one. For small Δt 's and $p \geq 4$, term $\mathcal{O}(h^{r+1}/\Delta t)$ in (21) becomes dominant and the error slightly increases
 328 when Δt decreases.

329 In addition, Fig. 6 shows that the errors of mass are significantly lower for the conservative method
 330 than for the non-conservative one. Indeed, for the conservative method, it seems that e_m does not have a
 331 clear dependence on Δt , which is due to the fact that scheme (13) is theoretically conservative irrespective
 332 of Δt . On the contrary, mass preservation in the non-conservative scheme (A.2) is as accurate as the proper
 333 scheme, and hence e_m behaves as $\mathcal{O}(\Delta t^p)$ —except for the case $p = 6$, in which the error is already small and
 334 thus roundoff starts to play a role. We recall that the mass preservation errors in the conservative method
 335 derive from inaccuracies in the computation of the right-hand side of Eq. (13), and thus could be even lower
 336 if we employed mesh intersection techniques [45–47].

Figure 6: L^2 and mass errors of Test I with respect to Δt for $r = 5$ and $h = 0.052$. Legend: (—) $p = 1$, (—) $p = 2$, (—) $p = 3$, (—) $p = 4$, (—) $p = 5$, (—) $p = 6$, (—) conservative scheme, (—) non-conservative scheme, (····) asymptote $\propto \Delta t^p$.

337 On the other hand, Fig. 7 shows the variation of the errors with respect to the mesh size h for a fixed
 338 time discretization. As can be seen, the asymptotic convergence $\mathcal{O}(h^{r+1})$ in the L^2 error is achieved for both

339 methods, although the errors are lower again for the conservative one. Note that, for very small h 's and
 340 $r \geq 4$, the error is already very small and no longer decreases as the mesh is refined, but oscillates notably
 341 with h . These oscillations may be due to the fact that this test considers the hard pure convection case
 342 and a velocity field with a strong anisotropic character, which makes that the solution be very sensitive
 343 to variations in the mesh geometry. The errors of mass are also smaller for the conservative method and
 344 generally decrease with h , although not with a clear rate.

Figure 7: L^2 and mass errors of Test I with respect to h for $p = 4$ and $\Delta t = 0.01$. Legend: (—) $r = 1$, (—) $r = 2$, (—) $r = 3$, (—) $r = 4$, (—) $r = 5$, (—) conservative scheme, (---) non-conservative scheme, (.....) asymptote $\propto h^{r+1}$.

345 4.2. Test II

346 The second test, which was proposed by Rui and Tabata to check the behavior of their first-order
 347 conservative Lagrange-Galerkin method [18], consists on a convection-diffusion problem given by

$$\epsilon = 0.01, \mathbf{a}(\mathbf{x}, t) = [1 + \sin(t - x_1), 1 + \sin(t - x_2)]^T, u(\mathbf{x}, t) = \exp\left(-\frac{2 - \cos(t - x_1) - \cos(t - x_2)}{\epsilon}\right), T = 0.5.$$

348 For simplicity, we have considered homogeneous Neumann conditions at the whole boundary, and $u(\mathbf{x}, t) = 0$
 349 for all \mathbf{x} outside the domain. The evolution of the solution from $t = 0$ to $t = T$ is shown in Fig. 8. It
 350 is worth remarking that, although there is some little flux entering through the boundary, mass remains
 351 approximately constant along time [18].

Figure 8: Numerical solution of Test II at different time instants. The horizontal and vertical axis correspond to the x_1 and x_2 coordinates, respectively.

352 Fig. 9 shows the dependence of the errors with respect to the parameter Δt for a fixed space discretization.
 353 As can be seen, the L^2 error behaves as $\mathcal{O}(\Delta t^p)$ for $p \leq 4$, and is smaller for the conservative method. For
 354 $p \geq 5$, the L^2 error is already very small and therefore the theoretical convergence rate is not appreciated.
 355 In addition, as with Test I, the errors of mass are much smaller and almost constant with respect to Δt for
 356 the conservative method, whereas for the non-conservative one they behave approximately as $\mathcal{O}(\Delta t^p)$.

Figure 9: L^2 and mass errors of Test II with respect to Δt for $r = 5$ and $h = 0.052$. Legend: (—) $p = 1$, (—) $p = 2$, (—) $p = 3$, (—) $p = 4$, (—) $p = 5$, (—) $p = 6$, (—) conservative scheme, (—) non-conservative scheme, (····) asymptote $\propto \Delta t^p$.

357 In addition, Fig. 10 shows the behavior of the errors with respect to the mesh size for a fixed time
 358 discretization. As with Test I, the L^2 error increases as $\mathcal{O}(h^{r+1})$, whereas the error of mass generally
 359 increases with h , although not with a clear dependence. Note that in this test the errors between both
 360 methods are much closer than in Test I –indeed, they are almost coincident. This is due to the fact that, in
 361 Test I, we employed schemes (13) and (A.2) which, at each step, require to project onto a displaced mesh the
 362 first and the p previous solutions, respectively. Therefore, (13) led to smaller errors. However, in this case,
 363 we are employing schemes (18) and (A.2), which require to project the same number of previous solutions.
 364 Thus, when the error due to the time discretization is negligible, both methods behave in a more similar
 365 way and lead to closer errors.

Figure 10: L^2 and mass errors of Test II with respect to h for $p = 4$ and $\Delta t = 0.01$. Legend: (—) $r = 1$, (—) $r = 2$, (—) $r = 3$, (—) $r = 4$, (—) $r = 5$, (—) conservative scheme, (---) non-conservative scheme, (····) asymptote $\propto h^{r+1}$.

366 Finally, as a way to check the quality of the results, we have repeated the experiments of Rui and Tabata
 367 [18] for this test. In the latter, each edge of the domain is divided into N uniform segments –from which the
 368 mesh is constructed– and $\Delta t = 2/N$ for different values of N . The initial condition is taken as $u_h^0 = L_h u^0(\mathbf{x})$
 369 –recall that L_h denotes the Lagrange interpolation operator onto V_h . Then, we measure the relative errors

$$\widehat{e}_{L^2} = \frac{\max_n \sqrt{\int_{\Omega} (u_h^n - L_h u^n)^2 \, d\Omega}}{\max_n \sqrt{\int_{\Omega} (L_h u^n)^2 \, d\Omega}}, \quad \widehat{e}_m = \frac{\left| \int_{\Omega} (u_h^{N_T} - L_h u^{N_T}) \, d\Omega \right|}{\left| \int_{\Omega} L_h u^{N_T} \, d\Omega \right|},$$

370 where $N_T = \lceil T/\Delta t \rceil$ denotes the last simulated time before T . Note that the authors in [18] employ a
 371 first-order-in-time method with linear elements. Also note that $\mathcal{O}(\Delta t) \sim \mathcal{O}(h)$ in these experiments, and
 372 thus the L^2 errors must converge as $\mathcal{O}(\Delta t^p) + \mathcal{O}(h^{r+1}/\Delta t) \sim \mathcal{O}(\Delta t^{\min\{p,r\}})$.

373 As can be seen in Fig. 11, we obtain slightly larger L^2 errors than [18] for the case $p = r = 1$. However,
 374 our method allows to consider higher-order discretizations that provide clearly better results. In addition, it
 375 can be checked that the L^2 error converges with Δt as expected for $p = r \leq 4$ –for $p = r = 5$, the convergence
 376 is more irregular, although the errors are still smaller. The errors of mass are also smaller in our method,
 377 although it must be pointed that we do not compute the right-hand side of (18) in the same way as [18].

Figure 11: Relative L^2 and mass errors for the numerical experiments in [18]. Legend: $(-\star-)$ Rui-Tabata method [18], $(-\square-)$ present method, $(-\square-)$ conservative scheme, $(-\ominus-)$ non-conservative scheme, (\cdots) asymptote $\propto \Delta t^p$.

378 4.3. Test III

379 Test III consists on the problem defined by

$$\epsilon = 0.01, u(\mathbf{x}, t) = 2.5 - \sin(\omega t) \cos(\lambda x_1) - \sin(\omega t) \cos(\lambda x_2),$$

$$\mathbf{a}(\mathbf{x}, t) = \frac{\epsilon \lambda^2 \sin(\omega t) + \omega \cos(\omega t)}{\lambda u(\mathbf{x}, t)} [\sin(\lambda x_1), \sin(\lambda x_2)]^T, \quad \omega = \frac{\pi}{2}, \lambda = \frac{3\pi}{4}, T = 1.$$

380 We apply Dirichlet boundary conditions at $x_1 = -1$ and $x_2 = -1$, and Neumann boundary conditions at $x_1 = 1$
 381 and $x_2 = 1$ –the values of these boundary conditions being readily deduced from the expression of $u(\mathbf{x}, t)$.
 382 Note that, in this test, the boundary conditions are not homogeneous nor constant. Also note that $\mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{n} > 0$
 383 and $-\epsilon \partial u / \partial n < 0$ across the boundaries, so there is mass leaving and entering the domain by convection and
 384 diffusion effects, respectively. The evolution of the solution from $t = 0$ to $t = T$ is shown in Fig. 12.

Figure 12: Numerical solution of Test III at different time instants. The horizontal and vertical axis correspond to the x_1 and x_2 coordinates, respectively.

385 Fig. 13 shows the variation of the errors with respect to the parameter Δt for a fixed space discretization.
 386 As can be seen, the L^2 error behaves as $\mathcal{O}(\Delta t^p)$ both for the conservative method (with $p \leq 4$) and for the

387 non-conservative one (with $p \leq 6$). For the conservative method and $p \geq 5$, the optimal convergence rate is
 388 not achieved again because the errors are already small and therefore roundoff effects become important. In
 389 any case, the L^2 error is smaller for the conservative scheme. On the other hand, it is seen that in this test
 390 the error of mass converges as $\mathcal{O}(\Delta t^p)$ also for the conservative method. This is due to the fact that, now,
 391 the mass is not constant, and thus the computation of the final mass is as accurate as the time-marching
 392 method. Nevertheless, this error is significantly smaller for the case of the conservative method.

Figure 13: L^2 and mass errors of Test III with respect to Δt for $r = 5$ and $h = 0.052$. Legend: (—) $p = 1$, (—) $p = 2$, (—) $p = 3$, (—) $p = 4$, (—) $p = 5$, (—) $p = 6$, (—□) conservative scheme, (—○) non-conservative scheme, (····) asymptote $\propto \Delta t^p$.

393 Furthermore, Fig. 14 shows the behavior of the errors with respect to the mesh size for a fixed time
 394 discretization. As with Test II, the L^2 error is similar for both methods and behaves as $\mathcal{O}(h^{r+1})$ as long
 395 as roundoff effects are not important. On the other hand, the errors of mass are generally smaller in the
 396 conservative method for $r \geq 3$, whereas for $r \leq 2$ they are smaller in the non-conservative method. This
 397 is due to the fact that the error of the considered time discretization $-p = 6$ and $\Delta t = 0.01-$ is negligible
 398 when compared to that of the space discretization—which is the same for both methods—, and therefore the
 399 conservative method can not stand out from the non-conservative one.

Figure 14: L^2 and mass errors of Test III with respect to h for $p = 6$ and $\Delta t = 0.01$. Legend: (—) $r = 1$, (—) $r = 2$, (—) $r = 3$, (—) $r = 4$, (—) $r = 5$, (—) conservative scheme, (---) non-conservative scheme, (.....) asymptote $\propto h^{r+1}$.

400 4.4. Test IV

401 The fourth test is an extension of Test II to three dimensions, which is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon &= 0.01, \mathbf{a}(\mathbf{x}, t) = [1 + \sin(t - x_1), 1 + \sin(t - x_2), 1 + \sin(t - x_3)]^T, \\ u(\mathbf{x}, t) &= \exp\left(-\frac{3 - \cos(t - x_1) - \cos(t - x_2) - \cos(t - x_3)}{\epsilon}\right), T = 0.5, \end{aligned}$$

402 with homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions and $u(\mathbf{x}, t) = 0$ for all \mathbf{x} outside the domain. The evolution
403 of the solution from $t = 0$ to $t = T$ is shown in Fig. 15.

Figure 15: Contour plots of the numerical solution of Test IV at the plane $x_1 = t$.

404 The results are very similar to those of previous tests. In effect, as it is seen in Fig. 16, for fixed h
405 and variable Δt , the L^2 and the mass errors are lower for the conservative method. In addition, it is seen
406 that the L^2 error behaves as $\mathcal{O}(\Delta t^p)$ for large Δt 's, whereas for small Δt 's the optimal convergence rate is
407 lost. On the other hand, the error of mass seems to be almost constant for the conservative method, and to
408 behave as $\mathcal{O}(\Delta t^p)$ for the non-conservative one.

Figure 16: L^2 and mass errors of Test IV with respect to Δt for P_2 elements and $h = 0.02245$. Legend: (—) $p = 2$, (—) $p = 3$, (—) conservative scheme, (- -) non-conservative scheme, (.....) asymptote $\propto \Delta t^p$.

409 Finally, Fig. 17 shows that, for a variable mesh size and a small enough Δt , the L^2 and mass errors are
 410 similar for the conservative and the non-conservative schemes, since the errors due to the time discretization
 411 are negligible and the space discretization is the same for both methods. Note that the L^2 error behaves as
 412 $\mathcal{O}(h^{r+1})$, whereas the error of mass decreases with h but not with a clear rate.

Figure 17: L^2 and mass errors of Test IV with respect to h for $p = 3$ and $\Delta t = 0.01$. Legend: (—) $r = 1$, (—) $r = 2$, (—) conservative scheme, (- -) non-conservative scheme, (.....) asymptote $\propto h^{r+1}$.

413 4.5. Run-time comparisons

414 In medium-scale problems –in which it is practical to store and factorize the matrices of systems (13) and
 415 (18)–, computational efficiency may be another advantage of the conservative method with respect to the
 416 non-conservative one. This stems from the fact that non-conservative scheme (A.2) leads to a linear system
 417 whose matrix depends on the term $\nabla \cdot \mathbf{a}^n$, and therefore has to be recomputed at every simulated instant.
 418 On the contrary, conservative scheme (18) leads to a linear system whose matrix is constant whenever the
 419 time step size is fixed –which happens for the most part of the simulation. Therefore, it avoids the cost of
 420 recomputing the system matrix and, in addition, allows to reuse the matrix factorization to accelerate the
 421 resolution of the system.

422 To illustrate this point, we have run again Test III with both methods, using different time-discretizations
 423 – $p = 2, 4, 6$ –, two different mesh sizes and P_5^{bubble} elements. Then, we have measured the average per
 424 simulated instant of the total run-time, of the time spent recomputing the system matrix, of the time
 425 computing the right-hand side term, and of the time spent solving the linear system. The initial steps
 426 –in which the time step size is not constant– have been excluded from the profiling times. Systems (18)
 427 and (A.2) are solved as follows. First, the system matrix is written as a 2×2 block matrix, whose blocks
 428 are related to the large-scale and to the fine-scale degrees of freedom. Since the submatrix related to the
 429 fine-scale terms is block diagonal, these terms can easily be condensed to provide a system written only in
 430 terms of the large-scale degrees of freedom. Then, the resulting system is solved via Cholesky –conservative
 431 method– or LDL –non-conservative method– factorization. The simulations were performed in a ten-core
 432 Intel i9-7900X CPU 3.30GHz machine with 32 GB of RAM.

433 The profiling times are shown in Tables 3 and 4 for approximately 10^4 and 10^5 mesh nodes, respectively.
 434 In effect, the total run-time per simulated instant is considerably smaller for the conservative method,
 435 irrespective of p , as a consequence of avoiding the computation of the system matrices and of a much
 436 faster resolution of the linear system². For the conservative method, it is also seen that most part of the
 437 computational effort is spent on the evaluation of the right-hand side term –in particular, on searching
 438 and locating the high amount of quadrature points of the convected mesh in the fixed mesh. Thus, its
 439 computational cost turns to be approximately proportional to p .

Table 3: Profiling times (in seconds) per simulated instant for 11941 nodes.

	Total	System matrix	R.h.s. term	System resolution
Cons., $p = 2$	0.3635	0.0	0.3317	0.003041
Cons., $p = 4$	0.6999	0.0	0.6424	0.00308
Cons., $p = 6$	1.083	0.0	0.9968	0.003246
Non-cons., $p = 2$	1.01	0.5973	0.2964	0.08941
Non-cons., $p = 4$	1.322	0.5937	0.5856	0.09034
Non-cons., $p = 6$	1.698	0.5908	0.9341	0.09183

Table 4: Profiling times (in seconds) per simulated instant for 100376 nodes.

	Total	System matrices	R.h.s. term	System resolution
Cons., $p = 2$	1.046	0.0	0.8977	0.01205
Cons., $p = 4$	2.031	0.0	1.759	0.01167
Cons., $p = 6$	3.152	0.0	2.742	0.01231
Non-cons., $p = 2$	3.351	2.012	0.8654	0.3487
Non-cons., $p = 4$	4.375	2.045	1.73	0.3481
Non-cons., $p = 6$	5.567	2.081	2.751	0.3486

²Of course, one may solve the linear systems in the non-conservative scheme more efficiently by using iterative methods instead of an LDL factorization. However, it would still be difficult to beat the conservative scheme in this point, as the latter employs a previously computed Cholesky decomposition and thus the resolution of the linear systems is almost immediate.

4.6. Work-precision diagrams of the conservative method

Next we study the relation between the L^2 error and the total CPU time (t_{CPU}) for different space and time discretizations in order to clarify which discretization orders are more efficient. As in Section 4.5, we consider Test III and exclude from the profiling times those initial steps in which the time step size is not constant. However, here the experiments were performed in parallel in a 64-core AMD Epyc 7601 CPU 2.20 GHz machine with 28GB of RAM (one experiment per core).

The results are shown in Fig. 18. As can be seen, for a fixed time discretization, high-order elements yield clearly more accurate results for the same CPU time (excepting the case in which roundoff errors become important). On the contrary, for a fixed space discretization, high-order time discretizations are only more accurate when the CPU time is larger than a certain value. The latter means that high-order time discretizations are more effective when the time step is small enough, in which case the faster convergence rate offsets the greater computational cost per simulated instant.

Figure 18: L^2 error of Test III versus CPU time (in seconds). Left: fixed time discretization with $p = 6$ and $\Delta t = 0.01$. Right: fixed space discretization with $r = 5$ and $h = 0.052$.

5. Conclusions

In this work, we present a novel (nearly) conservative, high-order, Lagrange-Galerkin method for the resolution of the scalar pure-convection and convection-dominated diffusion equations in non-divergence-free velocity fields.

The scheme is based on formulating a conservation equation for a *weighted mass*, which can be easily discretized in time and in space with any order of accuracy, and from which the conservation equation for the standard mass can be seen as a particular case. In addition, the scheme is posed so that it leads to linear systems of equations with constant and symmetric positive definite matrices –whenever the mesh and the time step are fixed–, and so that the terms that appear in the formulation can be readily computed by means of standard operations with respect to some displaced isoparametric curvilinear meshes.

The method has been tested on three 2D problems using up to sixth-order time-marching schemes and fifth-order finite element discretizations, as well as on a 3D problem using up to third-order time discretizations and second-order finite elements. Numerical experiments show that the L^2 error of the method behaves as expected from the theory of Lagrange-Galerkin methods. In addition, the present method

466 results to be generally more accurate than the classic one –especially in terms of mass conservation errors–
 467 and clearly outperforms the latter in terms of efficiency for medium-scale problems. Mass conservation
 468 is not fully achieved due to the inexact computation of some integrals, although this could be alleviated
 469 by employing mesh intersection techniques [45–47]. Results also show good agreement with those of other
 470 authors [18].

471 To the best of our knowledge, the present method is the first conservative, Lagrange-Galerkin scheme
 472 that takes into account both non-divergence-free velocity fields and space and time discretizations of any
 473 order. Thus, we hope it provides some help in the numerical resolution of convection-dominated problems in
 474 the presence of non-divergence-free velocity fields. Some works could be addressed in the future, such as to
 475 implement mesh intersection techniques [45–47] to increase the accuracy in the computation of some integrals
 476 in the formulation, to enforce mass conservation with machine-precision accuracy via Lagrange multipliers
 477 [61], to perform a theoretical analysis of the error and of the stability of the method, to implement mesh
 478 adaptation strategies [13, 62] and to extend the method to the more complex case of the compressible
 479 Navier-Stokes equations.

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485 Appendix A. Classical, non-conservative Lagrange-Galerkin method

486 For comparison purposes, we briefly review next the standard Lagrange-Galerkin formulation for both
 487 pure convection and convection-diffusion problems. The reader is referred to [15–17, 39] for more details.

488 The classical method is based on writing Eq. (1) as

$$\frac{Du}{Dt} = -(\nabla \cdot \mathbf{a})u + \nabla \cdot (\epsilon \nabla u), \quad (\text{A.1})$$

489 which is integrated along the trajectories of the fluid particles, i.e.,

$$\frac{du(\mathbf{X}(\mathbf{x}, t^n; t), t)}{dt} = [-(\nabla \cdot \mathbf{a}(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{t}))u(\mathbf{X}, t) + \nabla \cdot (\epsilon(\mathbf{X}, t)\nabla u(\mathbf{X}, t))] \Big|_{\mathbf{X}=\mathbf{X}(\mathbf{x}, t^n; t)}.$$

490 If we apply a BDF p formula to the latter equation and discretize in space with the finite element methodology,
 491 we eventually arrive at

$$\sum_{k=0}^p \alpha_k (u_h^{n-l} \circ \mathbf{X}^{n-l}, v_h^n)_{\Omega_h} + \Delta t^n ((\nabla \cdot \mathbf{a})^n u_h^n, v_h^n)_{\Omega_h} + \Delta t^n (\epsilon \nabla u_h^n, \nabla v_h^n)_{\Omega_h} + \Delta t^n S_{\text{LPS}}(u_h^n, v_h^n) = \Delta t^n \left\langle \epsilon \frac{\partial u^n}{\partial n}, v_h^n \right\rangle_{\partial \Omega_h}, \quad (\text{A.2})$$

492 which can be implemented in a way similar to schemes (13) and (18). However, it must be noted that the
 493 latter scheme is not conservative, and neither is, in general, any scheme derived from (A.1). Indeed, if we
 494 consider $\epsilon = 0$ for simplicity, the conservation equation associated to (A.1) is

$$\int_{\Omega_h} \frac{Du}{Dt} d\Omega + \int_{\Omega_h} (\nabla \cdot \mathbf{a})u d\Omega = 0,$$

495 which, unlike (11), is not posed so that mass is preserved despite the errors due to the time discretization.
 496 Hence, in schemes derived from (A.1), the errors of mass are as accurate as the space and time discretizations,
 497 as it is seen in the numerical examples.

498 Another inconvenient of (A.2) with respect to (13) and (18) is that it leads to a system whose matrix
 499 depends on $(\nabla \cdot \mathbf{a})^n$, which is generally non-constant, and therefore has to be recomputed at each simulated
 500 instant.

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